

Fait clinique

Small-cell bronchial cancer complicated by ischemic stroke of emboligenic tumor origin in a 25-year-old Malagasy man: a case report

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Reçu le 14/07/2023, accepté après correction le 25/01/2024, disponible en ligne le 01/02/2024

Keywords : Small cell cancer; Tuberculosis of the lung; Tumor emboli; Young adult.

Abstract

Small-cell bronchopulmonary cancer remains rare in young adults, particularly when associated with clinical presentations of ischemic stroke of tumoral emboligenic origin. We report a rare case of small-cell bronchopulmonary cancer in a 25-year-old Malagasy man, discovered after failure to improve clinically despite anti-tuberculosis treatment for pulmonary tuberculosis in a context of a voluminous left lower lobar lung mass with cardiac invasion. An ischemic stroke of emboligenic tumor origin complicated the situation. Despite chemotherapy with initially favorable results, tumor progression led to the patient's death. Bronchial cancer should be looked for in the face of clinical worsening despite well-conducted treatment in a tuberculosis patient.

Mots clés : Adulte jeune; Cancer à petites cellules; Embolie tumorale; Tuberculose du poumon.

Résumé

Le cancer bronchopulmonaire à petites cellules demeure rare chez les sujets jeunes, notamment lorsqu'elle est associée à des présentations cliniques d'AVC ischémique d'origine emboligène tumorale. Nous rapportons un cas rare de cancer bronchique à petites cellules chez un jeune malgache de 25 ans découvert au décours d'une absence d'amélioration clinique malgré un traitement antituberculeux devant une tuberculose pulmonaire avérée dans un contexte de volumineuse masse pulmonaire lobaire inférieure gauche avec envahissement cardiaque. Un AVC ischémique d'origine emboligène tumorale a compliqué la situation. Malgré une chimiothérapie avec des résultats favorables initialement, la progression tumorale conduisait au décès du patient. Un cancer bronchique est à rechercher devant une aggravation clinique malgré un traitement bien conduit chez un tuberculeux.

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Introduction

Bronchial cancer rarely occurs in young adults, ranging from 5% to 12.5% in those under 50 years old (1). In young adults, bronchial adenocarcinoma is the most common histological type, while cases of small-cell lung cancer are relatively low (2-5). The clinical characteristics of small-cell cancers differ greatly from those of elderly subjects in terms of demographic and prognostic parameters (5). All the reported cases of tumor emboli causing ischemic stroke related to tumor infiltration of the left atrium and pulmonary veins concerned elderly subjects (6-8). Our aim was to report a rare case of disseminated small-cell bronchial cancer complicated by ischemic stroke of tumor embolism origin in a young man, discovered after a lack of clinical improvement despite a well-administered course of antituberculosis treatment for pulmonary tuberculosis.

Observation

This is the case of a 25-year-old man, driver, smoking 2 pack-years, with no personal or family history of cancer, initially diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis on a GeneXpert examination for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and treated with quadritherapy of Rifampicin, Isoniazid, Pyrazinamide, Ethambutol according to the national protocol. The evolution after four months of treatment was not favorable, with the progressive onset of intense and permanent left chest pain associated with exertional dyspnea with asthenia and anorexia, evolving in an afebrile context. He was then hospitalized in a pneumology department. Physical examination revealed a conscious patient with a PS (Performans Status) of 1. Physical examination revealed a percutaneous oxygen saturation of 98% on room air, polypnoea with signs of respiratory struggle, and diminished vesicular murmurs in the lower

left third, without cardiac congestive signs. Testicular palpation was normal and there were no lymph nodes. The rest of the examination was normal. The chest X-ray revealed left atelectasis (Figure 1), and the chest CT showed a voluminous left lung mass measuring 108 x 104 mm, predominantly in the lower lobe, extending to the chest wall and mediastinum, with infiltration of the left pulmonary veins and left atrium, associated with circumferential pericardial effusion (Figure 2).

Figure 1 : Chest X-ray showing left atelectasis

Figure 2 : Chest CT scan showing a left lower lobar lung mass extending to the chest wall and mediastinum.

Bronchial endoscopy revealed extrinsic compression of the left bronchial stump. Pathological examination of bronchial biopsies revealed a respiratory epithelial surface overlying a submucosa infiltrated by cohesive clusters of cells with atypical, basophilic nuclei, sparse cytoplasm and associated crush artifacts. The atypical cells were positive for anti-synaptophysin, chromogranin and CD 56 immunostaining, concluding in small-cell neuroendocrine infiltrating lung carcinoma. During his hospitalization, the patient presented with right hemiparesis and aphasia of abrupt onset, spontaneously reversible. The CT scan was consistent with a recent ischemic stroke in the left superficial sylvian territory (Figure 3).

Figure 3 : Cerebral CT scan showing hypodensity in the territory of the left anterior cerebral artery and the left middle cerebral artery, in favor of an ischemic stroke in the territory of the left superficial sylvian artery.

For the etiological investigation, cardiac echo-

mass infiltrating the left atrium, associated with a non-compressive pericardial effusion of moderate size, explaining the tumoral emboligenic origin of the ischemic stroke (Figure 4).

Figure 4 : Cardiac ultrasound showing a homogeneous isoechoic mass infiltrating the left atrium.

The abdominal CT revealed involvement of the left adrenal gland. The small-cell lung cancer is classified as disseminated. After a multi-disciplinary consultation meeting, the patient was managed by the oncologists, and chemotherapy was started according to the standard concomitant protocol, with 4 cycles on D1 = D22 of Cisplatin-Etoposide at a dosage of 80mg/m² for Cisplatin and 100mg/m² for Etoposide. The reassessment after 4 months of chemotherapy revealed a good tumor response, with a regression of 60% of the lung mass and disappearance of the adrenal nodule. The chemotherapy continued with the same therapeutic protocol for up to 6 cycles. Due to a lack of financial resources, chemotherapy was performed once a month from the 4th cycle, and then the 5th cycle of chemotherapy was not performed. A thoraco-abdomino-pelvic CT scan performed 6 months after the last

re-evaluation showed tumor progression, with the appearance of a heterogeneous left mediastino-hilar lymph node formation measuring 44 x 63 mm, compressing the left bronchus and cardiac cavities, and the appearance of a liver lesion. Monofractionated pulmonary and mediastinal radiotherapy at a dose of 60 Gy over 30 sessions was performed. Disease progression persisted, with adrenal damage and new liver and brain lesions. The patient stopped attending chemotherapy sessions regularly. The patient died approximately 21 months after diagnosis.

Discussion

This case demonstrates the possibility of small-cell lung cancer occurring in young subjects. It illustrates the real diagnostic and therapeutic difficulty of lung cancer in Madagascar, since tuberculosis during treatment masked the signs of pulmonary neoplasia. Secondly, until now, cases of tumor emboli in small-cell bronchial cancer reported in the literature have rarely occurred in young subjects, which makes this case original.

This case study has limitations : the lack of financial resources limited therapeutic management according to established protocols and regular patient follow-up.

Several studies of bronchial cancers in young subjects have been reported, but the occurrence of small-cell bronchial cancer remained low, with an incidence of 0.6% from 1978 to 2010 in a study carried out in the USA (5). Meanwhile, Serhane et al described a series of 51 cases of bronchial cancer in young adults under 50, in which only 4 cases were small-cell cancers (4). Moreover, Jubelirer et al. and Chellal et al. found 3.5% and 3% small-cell bronchial cancers respectively, compared with 54% and 79.5% bronchial adenocarcinomas (3,9).

Pulmonary tuberculosis is a risk factor of lung cancer (10). The relative risk of developing

bronchial cancer in subjects with a history of tuberculosis is 1.76, and the risk is multiplied by 2 twenty years after the diagnosis of tuberculosis (11). In this case, the diagnosis of small-cell bronchial cancer was made 4 months after the diagnosis of pulmonary tuberculosis. The high endemicity of tuberculosis in Madagascar and the rarity of bronchial cancers in young subjects may explain why bronchial cancer is not investigated as soon as pulmonary tuberculosis is diagnosed. In fact, the clinical symptoms are identical, which makes the diagnosis difficult, since tuberculosis can simulate both symptoms and imaging, and bronchial cancer usually goes undetected (12). In Madagascar, improving the time taken to diagnose bronchial cancer remains a challenge, since studies carried out in the country show that the time taken remains very long compared with recommendations (13). In a study carried out in Madagascar, Refeno et al reported two cases of tuberculosis and bronchial cancer diagnosed simultaneously (14).

No cases of tumor emboli from small-cell bronchial cancer causing ischemic stroke in young subjects have been reported to date, with most occurring in elderly subjects (6-8). The 2 mechanisms of tumor emboli are tumor infiltration of myocardial tissue by contiguity and tumor extension to the left atrium via the pulmonary veins (15,16). Tumor emboli are most frequently reported at the aortic bifurcation or femoral vessels (50%) and in the cerebral circulation (30%) (17,18). Cardiac ultrasonography is essential for the detection of tumor emboli in lung cancer, given the presence of infiltration of the left atrium and pulmonary veins (19).

Conclusion

This case demonstrates that the diagnosis of small-cell bronchial cancer should not be ruled out in young adults, and despite a well-administered anti-tuberculosis treatment, a lack of improvement could be in favor of an association with bronchial cancer. The presence of a malignant pulmonary mass invading the pulmonary veins should lead to systematic cardiac echodoppler to look for infiltration of the left atrium and pulmonary veins, which could lead to a tumor embolus.

Bibliography

- [1]- Ramalingam S, Pawlish K, Gadgeel S, Demers R, Kalemkerian GP. Lung cancer in young patients: analysis of a surveillance, epidemiology, and end results database. *J Clin Oncol.* 1998;16(2):651-7.
- [2]- Ziane F, Adila F, Djeghri Y, Zitouni A. Le profil clinique, histologique et moléculaire des cancers bronchopulmonaires primitifs du sujet jeune : étude rétrospective portant sur 70 patients. *Rev Mal Respir.* 2021;13(1):125.
- [3]- Chellal H, Behbeh S, Ketfi A. Le cancer bronchique chez les sujets jeunes moins de 50 ans (À propos de 34 cas). *Rev Mal Respir.* 2022;14(1):204.
- [4]- Serhane H, Ouardi O, Ait Batahar A, Sajjai H, Amro L, Alaoui Yazidi A. Le cancer bronchique primitif chez le sujet jeune (à propos de 51 cas). *Rev Mal Respir.* 2015;32:A126.
- [5]- Thomas A, Chen Y, Yu T, Jakopovic M, Giaccone G. Trends and characteristics of young non-small cell lung cancer patients in the United States. *Front Oncol.* 2015;5:113.
- [6]- Chan V, Neumann D. Small cell lung carcinoma invading the pulmonary vein and left atrium as imaged by PET/CT. *J Nucl Med Mol Imaging.* 2005 Dec;32(12):1493.
- [7]- Gabrielli R, Rosati MS, Chiappa R, Vitale S, Millarelli M, Caselli G. Multiple instances of peripheral artery emboli from occult primary small cell lung cancer. *Tex Heart Inst J.* 2012;39(3):420-3.
- [8]- Lestuzzi C, Viel E, Mimo R, Meneguzzo N. Left atrial invasion by lung carcinoma through a pulmonary vein. *Int J Cardiovasc Imaging.* 2001;17(2):107-10.
- [9]- Jubelirer SJ, Wilson RA. Lung cancer in patients younger than 40 years of age. *Cancer.* 1991;67(5):1436-8.
- [10]- Zheng W, Blot WJ, Liao ML, Wang ZX, Levin LI, Zhao JJ, Fraumeni Jr JF, Gao YT. Lung cancer and prior tuberculosis infection in Shanghai. *Br J Cancer.* 1987;56(4):501-4.
- [11]- Brenner DR, McLaughlin JR, Hung RJ. Previous lung diseases and lung cancer risk: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One.* 2011;6(3):e17479.
- [12]- Vento S, Lanzafame M. Tuberculosis and cancer: a complex and dangerous liaison. *Lancet Oncol.* 2011;12(6):520-2.
- [13]- Ravahatra K, Tiaray Harison M, Rakotondrasoa OF, Ramirana EL, Rakotondrabe ID, Rasoafaranirina MO et al. Le délai diagnostique des cancers bronchopulmonaires vus à l'USFR de Pneumologie Befelatanana, Antananarivo, Madagascar. *Pan Afr Med J.* 2019;33:263.
- [14]- Refeno V, Hasiniatsy NRE, Andrianandrasana NOTF, Ramahandrisoa AVN, Rakotonarivo JM, Maevazaka JL et al. Aspects cliniques des cancers bronchopulmonaires primitifs au service d'oncologie du CHUA-HUJRA Antananarivo. *Pan Afr Med J.* 2015; 22: 271.
- [15]- Guha S, Mookerjee S, Karmakar RN, Mani S, Pande A, Bhattacharya R, Hema MB. Left atrial extension of lung malignancy with ECG changes resembling STEMI. *Indian Heart J.* 2010;62(1):81-3.
- [16]- Watanabe N, Kubo K. Images in cardiology : Intra-left atrial invasive mass extended via the pulmonary vein. *Heart.* 2001;85(3):271.
- [17]- Isada LR, Salcedo EE, Homa DA, Cohen GI, Rice TW. Intraoperative transesophageal echocardiographic localization of tumor embolus during pneumonectomy. *J Am Soc Echocardiogr.* 1992;5(5):551-4.
- [18]- Whyte RI, Starkey TD, Orringer MB. Tumor emboli from lung neoplasms involving the pulmonary vein. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg.* 1992;104(2):421-5.
- [19]- Ascione L, Granata G, Accadia M, Marasco G, Santangelo R, Tuccillo B. Ultrasonography in embolic stroke : the complementary role of transthoracic and transesophageal echocardiography in a case of systemic embolism by tumor invasion of the pulmonary veins in a patient with unknown malignancy involving the lung. *Eur J Echocardiogr.* 2004;5(4):304-7.